

Supplementary Figure S1. Maximum likelihood tree for *Neosalanx taihuensis* and other members of the family Salangidae based on the *COI* gene

Figure S1. Maximum likelihood tree of the *COI* gene sequences for *Neosalanx taihuensis* and other members of the family Salangidae. The Kimura 2-parameter (K2+G+I) model was used to infer the tree. The vertical bars (Lineage 1 and Lineage 2) show two significantly diverged clusters of species including the *N. taihuensis* specimens. The numerals at the nodes are bootstrap percent probability values based on 10,000 replicates (values lower than 75% are omitted). The *N. jordani* *COI* sequences were taken from Guo et al. [1] (HM151572, HM151572, and HM151572). The *N. taihuensis* MW291630 mitogenome is highlighted in red. For tree reconstruction we used only some representative samples from larger datasets (a full list of the sequences is provided in Supplementary Table S1). The outgroup species: *Plecoglossus altivelis* (AB047553) (genus *Plecoglossus*, family Plecoglossidae) and *Retropinna retropinna* (AP004108) (genus *Retropinna*, family Retropinnidae).

References

1. Guo, L.; Li, J.; Wang, Z.; Fu, C. Phylogenetic relationships of noodle-fishes (Osmeriformes: Salangidae) based on four mitochondrial genes. *Acta Hydrobiol. Sinica* 2011, 35, 449–459. DOI 10.3724/SP.J.1035.2011.00449